

ISLAMIC BUSINESS COMMUNICATION ETHICS

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Abstract

Islamic business communication ethics is an important study that combines the principles of effective communication with Islamic ethical values. In a business context, good communication does not only focus on delivering clear messages but must also reflect honesty, fairness, and social responsibility as stipulated in Islamic teachings. This study aims to explore how Islamic ethics can be applied in business communication to enhance trust and good relations between the parties involved. The literature research method is used to collect and analyze various related sources including the Quran, Hadith, and contemporary literature on business ethics and communication. The results of this study indicate that by adopting Islamic ethics in business communication, companies can not only achieve their commercial goals effectively but also build a good and sustainable reputation in society. This study emphasizes the importance of integrating Islamic values in modern business operations to create an ethical and harmonious work environment.

Keyword: ISLAMIC BUSINESS, COMMUNICATION ETHICS

Introduction

Communication is the activity of exchanging messages between two or more parties. While business communication is the exchange of messages that have a purpose and are within the scope of business activities. Islamic business communication means the activity of exchanging messages between two or more parties within the scope of business based on Islamic rules. So, all forms of messages that come out of the communicator must pay attention to various Islamic ethics and principles. This includes all forms of business activities, whether related to products, company services, or communication with various parties to facilitate various business interests. This study explains the ethics of communication and business from a more comprehensive Islamic perspective based on the results of a literature review. The

method used is qualitative with a literature review approach which is carried out by reviewing several literatures related to the focus of the research through journal articles and books and other supporting data. The results of this writing show that in practice the application of Islamic principles includes unity, balance, free will, responsibility, and good deeds. The principles of Islamic business must also be accompanied by the implementation of good Islamic communication as stated in the Qur'an about qaulan ma'ruf, qaulan tsabit, qaulan sadid, qaulan bhaliqh, qaulan karim, qaulan maysur and qaulan layyin. If these two aspects are applied in business communication then everything will go well because everything we do has been blessed by Allah SWT. An Arabic proverb says, "Words are magic." As is known, this has been confirmed by Psychology because according to theory, words can have a very strong influence on a person's emotions and health. As the Messenger of Allah صلى الله عليه وسلم said, "Whoever believes in Allah and the Last Day should say good or keep quiet," (HR Bukhari and Muslim). The ability to communicate for humans is also the ability to build social relationships (business). It is a gift from Allah جل جلاله for humans themselves, so that humans can live in harmony on this earth. The business world in the future is faced with fierce competition, companies that have mature management will be superior and can survive long. In this case, business communication is one of the important elements that can be used by companies to achieve their goals, in meeting market targets and being able to create and influence the minds of potential consumers to buy the products they offer. Basically, for Muslims when doing business is not only to get abundant profits. But also get blessings for every transaction that exists. Therefore, there needs to be ethics in communicating in business. Which ethics is a reflection of the integrity of business actors in determining attitudes and behavior to interact with others. One of them is the honesty of business actors, which honesty is the main capital in doing business according to Sharia. In business communication ethics, it is not only about being honest and true, business actors must have other variables such as: Self-control, social responsibility, identity, healthy competition, and the concept of sustainable development. If the variables with moral and ethical values are fulfilled, there will be no black business (business that justifies any means) in the business world itself. As explained by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), the profits from the plagiarism industry worldwide in 2016 reached 460 billion US dollars, almost twice Indonesia's annual state budget. More than 62% of counterfeit products come from China and US brands are the most frequently pirated, especially Nike and Apple. Talking about business communication ethics, we cannot escape from the discussion of

communication ethics and business ethics where each field has its own explanation. Communication ethics can be said to be a series of basic principles or rules in conducting communication, which cover all components of the communication process. While what is meant by business ethics is how to carry out business activities, which cover all aspects related to individuals, companies, industries, and also society. While ethics itself comes from Latin, meaning moral philosophy and is a correct way of life seen from the perspective of culture, morality and religion. Communication in the business world is not an easy implementation. Because it takes communication skills to create effective communication in a business environment. Facts on the ground show that in the business world there are often conflicts caused by business communication barriers. For example, misunderstandings due to unclear information. Every business organization must emphasize the importance of business communication ethics, this is important because it can build good relationships with work relations, the community, or shareholders.

Research methods

The literature research method is an approach used to collect information and data from various written sources, such as books, scientific journals, research reports, articles, and other relevant documents. This process involves identifying, critically reviewing, and synthesizing existing information to gain a deep understanding of the topic being studied. Researchers will usually start by identifying a research question or hypothesis, then searching for and selecting sources that can provide answers or related information. After that, researchers will read, assess, and analyze the collected data, and organize it systematically to provide a comprehensive picture of the issue being studied. The purpose of the literature research method is to base research arguments or findings on strong and reliable references from existing literature.

Results and Discussion

Business Ethics and Communication

Ethics are rules, norms, rules, or procedures that are commonly used as guidelines or principles for an individual in carrying out actions and behavior. In this case, the perspective of the object is human actions, attitudes, or actions. The specific definition of ethics is the science of the attitudes and morality of an individual in their social environment which is thick with rules and principles related to behavior that is considered correct. While the general definition of ethics is the rules, norms, rules, or procedures that are commonly used as guidelines or principles for an individual in carrying out actions and behavior. The application of this norm is closely related to the

good and bad nature of individuals in society. Thus, Ethics is the science that studies the good and bad as well as the obligations, rights, and responsibilities, both socially and morally, of each individual in their social life. Or it can also be said that ethics includes values related to individual morals related to right and wrong. The Great Dictionary of the Indonesian Language recognizes ethics as: The science of what is good and what is bad, and of moral rights and obligations, A collection of principles or values concerning morals and Values concerning right and wrong that are adopted by a group or society

Ethics in Greek Ethics comes from the Greek, *ethos*. It means custom (costum), or custom. action. Viewed from the perspective of its origin, ethics is more about the study of human habits. Which discusses all habits (customs) based on something inherent in human nature itself. In the discussion of ethics as a benchmark for good and bad habits in human behavior. So, everything that ethics wants to investigate is habits in the sense of morality (morality). Therefore, ethics is often said to be the study of right or wrong in human behavior.

Ethics in Arabic Ethics is equivalent to the word *akhlaq* and its equivalent in the Qur'an is *khuluq*. This can be understood in the explanation of Q.S. Al-Qalam Verse 4:61 ﴿” And indeed you are of a great moral character”. According to M. Quraish Shihab, the verse above explains the appointment of the Prophet Muhammad SAW as the Messenger of Allah. The role of the Messenger as a role model for all mankind. According to Soegarda Pocrbakawatja, ethics is everything about values or science that studies good and bad for human life, more on the mindset and feelings that are considered for acting in achieving certain goals. The conclusion of the three definitions above, we can see that ethics is morals or morals in the values of bad and good behavior of a person to the surrounding environment. Which moral is said to be humanistic anthropocentis, namely everything that comes from, by and for humans. Also, these actions are certainly in accordance with the behavioral patterns produced by human reason based on the revelation of Allah, namely the Qur'an, the customs of the general public, or existing regulations. In business, ethics can be interpreted as an ethical rule regarding the benchmark for whether or not business activities are right or wrong, covering various aspects of business activities at the individual, company or community level.

The Purpose of Business Communication Ethics

Basically, business ethics are encouraged because they have certain intentions and goals in the business world. The purpose of business ethics is to run and create a

business as fairly as possible and to adjust to the laws that have been made. In addition, it is also intended to eliminate dependence on an individual or company position. Business ethics also become a plus or advantage for a company, both in the long and medium term. The functions of business ethics include being able to reduce funds resulting from the prevention of possible friction or division, both from within the company itself and externally. Other functions of business ethics are to raise employee motivation to continue to increase, protect the principle of freedom of trade or commerce, and can create competitive advantage. In general, an unethical company action will make consumers become provoked and eventually an act of retaliation will emerge. For example, the prohibition of the circulation of a product, the boycott movement, and the like, then what happens is a decrease in the selling value and also the company. This is certainly different from a company that values business ethics, it will definitely get a higher satisfaction rating. Business ethics certainly has its own benefits for the company. If a company applies business ethics optimally and continuously, the company will get several benefits, including the following:

First, Improving the Company's reputation. Companies that pay attention to business ethics can help improve their positive image in the market and society. Of course, this can attract new customers through the 'mouth to mouth' marketing system. Likewise, if you do not pay attention to this business ethics properly, the company can get a negative image from the market or customers. This can reduce your chances of getting new customers, especially on social media. When customers are not satisfied with your service, they will usually spread information about their negative experiences transacting with you on social media.

Second, the company becomes more trusted. Companies that always prioritize business ethics can make the company more trusted in the eyes of customers. With this business ethics, companies can show that their company is always honest and never deceives its customers. With the trust of consumers, the company will be considered loyal in doing their business with consumers. In the end, consumers will recommend your company as a company that can be trusted to meet their needs.

Third, the company can adapt to change. Employees who have business ethics in the workplace are the main key to the success of the company. They will have understanding, can be trusted, can be relied on, have motivation, attention and also be responsible by adapting to all positions and jobs given to them. When the company experiences a shortage of employees because some employees leave the company due to changes, then employees who have business ethics can be trusted and are responsible for the changes. They will try to maximize their work. Fourth, Creating a

unique corporate culture. The application of business ethics in the company will create and shape a unique corporate culture and create excellence in the company. With the formation of this unique culture, it will create a contribution to the values and norms that apply to the company. With this, business ethics can help to develop the company to be better.

Principles of Business Ethics

In Islam, the prerequisite for achieving blessings on transcendent values, a business person must pay attention to several ethical principles that have been outlined in Islam, including: First, honesty in quantity. Honesty in this measure is very important to note because God Himself clearly says: "Woe to those who cheat. If they measure from others (for themselves), they fill them up (their measurements). But if they measure (for others) or weigh (for others), they reduce them." The issue of honesty is not only the key to the success of a business person according to Islam. But modern business ethics also emphasizes the principle of honesty. According to Byham above, business ethics builds trust and trust is the basis of modern business. If we accept this view that there are no two moralities, namely for individuals and for business, but rather a general moral framework that applies to both individual and group activities. As for philosophers, they are seen as a morally happy life. This means that in all relationships, trust is a fundamental element. Trust is generated from sincerity. Sincerity is one of the character qualities that is so difficult to achieve in business activities, family or other places where one's self-interest competes with the interests of others. In business to build a framework of trust, a trader must be able to act honestly or fairly, both to himself and to others. This honesty must be realized, among others, in the practice of using scales that do not distinguish between personal interests (sellers) and others (buyers). With an honest attitude, the buyer's trust in the seller will be created by itself. Second, selling goods of good quality (quality). One of the ethical flaws in the view is not being transparent in terms of quality, which means ignoring moral responsibility in the business world. Whereas the responsibility that is expected is a responsibility that is balanced (balance) between gaining profit (profile) and fulfilling the basic norms of society, both in the form of law, ethics or customs. Third, it is forbidden to use oaths (al-qasm). Often found in everyday life, especially among lower-class traders, what is known as an oath sale. They too easily use oaths with the intention of convincing buyers that their merchandise is truly of good quality in the hope that people will be encouraged to buy it. In Islam, such actions are not permitted because they will also eliminate blessings as the Messenger of Allah said: From Abu Hurairah r.a. I heard the Messenger of Allah. Said: "The oath promotes

trade, but destroys blessings (HR. Abu Dawud)."

Fourth, be loose and generous (tatsamuh and taraahum). In a transaction, contact occurs between the seller and the buyer. In this case, a seller is expected to be friendly and generous to every buyer. With this attitude, a seller will receive blessings in sales and will be sought after by buyers. The key to success is one, namely service to others. A hadith narrated by al-Turmudhi from 'Ikrimah ibn 'Ammar from Abu Zumayl from Malik ibn Marthad from his father, from Abi Dharr, which reads: Rasulullah SAW said: "Your smile to your brother is charity for you" (HR. Al-Turmudhi). Isn't a smile from a seller to a buyer a reflection of a friendly attitude that soothes the heart so that buyers will feel happy. And it is not impossible that in the end they will become loyal customers who will benefit business development in the future. Fifth, build good relationships (interrelationship/silat al-rahym) between colleagues. Islam emphasizes constructive relationships with anyone, including fellow business actors. As the Prophet Muhammad SAW said. Narrated by al-Bukhari: "That the Messenger of Allah SAW said: Whoever hopes for his sustenance to be made easy and his life to be prolonged, then he should establish a relationship of silaturrahmi (HR. al- Bukhari)." In relation to business, the meaning of sustenance being made easy and life being prolonged can mean that for business actors who often carry out silaturrahim (interrelationships) the business ventures they do will develop. Sixth, orderly administration. In the world of trade, it is natural for borrowing and lending practices to occur.

Conclusion

Ethics are morals or morals in the values of bad and good behavior of a person towards the surrounding environment. Which moral is said to be humanistic anthropocentis, namely everything that comes from, by and for humans. Also, these actions are certainly in accordance with the behavioral patterns produced by reason (عقل humans rely on the revelation of Allah (al-Qur'an), the customs of the general public, or existing regulations.

Business communication ethics in the perspective of Sharia are guidelines for good mu'amalah based on the Qur'an and hadith, including: 1) honesty, accuracy of information, trustworthy and responsible, constructive criticism, fair, not cheating, being of service & humility, not taking bribes, not liking to badmouth, and not liking to suspect.

Business communication is a key aspect in generating profits in business activities. However, these benefits are not only felt by capital holders or shareholders,

but also by all stakeholders who play a role in the company's operations, both directly and indirectly. This is intended so that business communication is based on business communication ethics so that it can go through various morals, including deontological, utilitarian, related to rights and justice. The Qur'an also explains the ethics of business communication that must be followed as a guideline for conducting business communication, namely qaulan sadida, qaulan zura, qaulan maisura and qaulan layyina. In addition, the Prophet Muhammad SAW also advised that business communication ethics must prioritize customer orientation and transparency. By following and practicing business communication ethics based on the verses of the Qur'an and the ethics of business communication of Rasullaullah SAW Insaallah the business efforts we do will be blessed and receive the blessing of Allah SWT. Business communication must be honest and open to the communicant, provide open space for anyone and any group to speak openly and transparently, and allow the community to freely express their views. In today's interconnected and highly competitive world, maintaining the trust of stakeholders, customers, and employees is paramount. Upholding business communication ethics will foster lasting relationships, enhance the company's reputation, and ensure long-term success.

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